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Brief Contents

1. **Central Himalayan Environment Association (Nga) And Rural Women :
A Study With Special Reference To Kumaun Region : A Case Study** 1-9
-DR. NAVAL JOSI, Almora (Uttarakhand) 10-13
2. **Mystical Approach In Different Relationship [With Special Reference To John
Donne, Shakespear, Gray And Eliot's Literary Works]** 14-18
-DR. Chanchal Sharma, Kanpur (U.P.) 14-18
3. **Role of Asanasand pranayama in treating hormonal imbalance** 19-21
-DR. Shaifali Agarwal, Moradabad (U.P.) 19-21
4. **The Sociol Economic and Environmental Impacts Of Renewable Energy
Expansion In Bhiwani Haryana** 22-25
-Punita Mishra, Jhunjhunu (Rajasthan) 22-25
5. **Art (Painting) Education In Madhya Pradesh With special reference
to Higher Education** 26-30
-1. DR. Alpana Upadhyay 2. Vinny Wadhwa, Ujjain (M.P.) 26-30
6. **Physiochemical Properties Of Ground Water In Blue Bird Wetland Hisar,
Haryana (India) With Special Reference To Higher Education** 31-33
-1. Kusum Lata 2. N.K. Mishra, Jhunjhunu (Rajasthan) 31-33
7. **Teachers , Education And Gender Discrimination** 34-39
-Vidushi Yadav, Moradabad (U.P.) 34-39
8. **A Comparative Study on Environmental Awareness among Senior Secondary
Level Students of U.P. Board and C.B.S.E. Board** 40-42
-DR. Shikha Banswal, Meerut (U.P.) 40-42
9. **Comparative Study Of Kho-kho Girls And Boys In Participation Of School
Competition In Mau District** 43-47
-DR. Amarjeet, Azamgarh (U.P.) 43-47
10. **संत साहित्य परंपरा में कबीर दास जी का योगदान** 48-50
-प्रदीप कुमार प्रजापति, जौनपुर (उ०प्र०) 48-50
11. **उच्च शिक्षा में गिरते मूल्यों का समाज में प्रभाव** 51-52
-डॉ० अर्चना श्रीवास्तव, बलिया (उ०प्र०) 51-52
12. **माध्यमिक स्तर के विद्यार्थियों की संचार माध्यमों के प्रति जागरूकता
का उनकी शैक्षिक उपलब्धि पर** 53-55
-राम लखन पाण्डेय, मीर्जापुर (उ०प्र०) 53-55
13. **बाल अपराधियों के संदर्भ में पुलिस की भूमिका** 56-59
-सुरेन्द्र पाल सिंह, आगरा (उ०प्र०) 56-59
14. **आर्य समाज के विभिन्न शिक्षण संस्थान** 60-61
-अखिलेश प्रताप सिंह, प्रयागराज (उ०प्र०) 60-61
15. **राष्ट्रपति महात्मा गांधी जी के अहिंसा का सिद्धान्त एवं आजाद भारत का लक्ष्य** 62-65
-डॉ० उषा सिंह, जौनपुर (उ०प्र०) 62-65
16. **आतंकवाद और धर्म** 66-68
-डॉ० आशुतोष कुमार, (उ०प्र०) 66-68
17. **भारतीय राष्ट्रवाद और डॉ० अंबेडकर** 66-68
-डॉ० शशिबाला, वाराणसी (उ०प्र०) 66-68

DR. Chanchal Sharma

Mystical Approach In Different Relationship [With Special Reference To John Donne, Shakespear, Gray And Eliot's Literary Works]

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Abstract: *In the present study I am trying to show the mystical approach in John Donne's poems, Along with Shakespeare, Gray and Eliot's literary works. John Donne has always known as a well renowned metaphysical poet. Metaphysical poets has known as men of learning and to show their study has their passion. 'The father of criticism Aristotle has rightly said about them as 'denominated poetry an imitative, writers will without wrong lose their right to the name of poets, for they cannot be said to have imitated anything they neither copied nature nor life. Their thoughts have often new but seldom natural. The present study has shown the different aspects of mysticism along with new approach of presence in absence in our different shades of realtions.*

Key Words: *Mysticism, Love, Religious, Presence, Absence, Metaphysical poets, Aristotle, imitative.*

John Donne a well known poet of the 17th century. He has always recognized as a metaphysical poet. Dryden rightly says of him he affects the metaphysics. 'His poems are full of farfetched allusions 'occult resemblances, paradoxes, riddles and hyperbole. When rightly look at Donne there he has two qualities, one is outspoken erotic and sensual. On the Other side earnest, sensual, passionate, complex and deep religious emotions. His divan poems have equally passionate mirroring the intense struggling of the sprite to conquer doubt and achieve faith. During 17th century he has given revolutionary types of poems. He has revolted against the traditional types of poems. His poems have highly intellectual impact. They have marked by bold and ingenious, conceits, imagery. Complexity and new thoughts. Donne poems have a combination of love and religious look. He always considered as a master of metaphysics conceit an extended metaphor that combines two vastly different ideas, often using imagery. One of the most famous of Donne's conceits has found in 'A Valediction Forbidding Morning 'Where he compared the apartness of two separated lovers to the working of the legs of a compass. Mysticism has a very important part of Donne's perms. Evelyn Underhill summarized the mysticism in this way' The mysticism to be the expression of the intimate tendency of human sprites towards a complete harmony with the transcendental order.

'Evelyn Underhill says that "Mysticism" lays down four chief characteristics of mysticism-

- 1) True mysticism is active and practical, not passive and theoretical.
- 2) Its aims are wholly transcendental and spiritual-the mystic's heart is always set upon the changeless one.
- 3) This one is for the mystic a living and personal object of love, that is, the business and method of mysticism is love.
- 4) Living union with this one is a definite state or form of enhanced life. This is arrived at by an arduous psychological and spiritual process-this so called "mystic way" leading to the unitive state. According to corollary "Mysticism is a sense of disinterestedness, self-surrender and pure love." Mysticism in fact variously defined ,but on one point almost all agree that mysticism has its origin in "that dim consciousness of the beyond which is a part of human nature and which is the raw material of all religious ,philosophy and art ."

There are two types of mysticism 1. Love Mysticism 2. ReligiousMysticism

Mysticism has a deep religious attitude of expression, deal with the supernatural or even the natural as a Vail that at once conceals and reveals the absolute. It has an intense realization of the difference between things of the world and great out worldly spiritual realties. It has a direct institutional experience of God through unifying love. His poems have full of mystical approach in different relationship of relations whether it has blood relation or other type of relations .His poems have purely literary full of wit and intellectual juggling. A valediction Forbidding Mourning has recognized a well known love mystical poem .Addressed to his beloved wife remarkable

for their sincerity and passion. The title of the poem reflect the theme the presence in absence. Inside the poem it has full of human emotions ,passions and different colures of love. The dedication has shown towards his wife. For example : "So let us melt ,and make no noise, Tear –floods, nor sigh–temped move.

'Twere Profanation of our joys,
To tell the laity of love.8

Again he has shown the concept of absence in these lines....
'Dull sublunary lovers 'love. Whose soul is sense cannot admit
Absence Because it doth remove
Those thing which elemented it 16.

With the help of these lines Donne has shown the obscurity and wants to shown the religious outlook. which everyone has not to be able to understand. Here he has also shown the absence aspect, where in the absence there the presence has always present. His love towards his wife has a sacramental commitment between him and his wife. With the help of these lines in 'valediction Forbidding Morning' he says.

'If they be two ,they are two so
As stiff twin compasses are two;
Thy soul ,the fixed food, makes no show
To move, but doth, if the other do. 25

As he has recognized as a love mystical poet therefore he has changed the traditional image of a love. He has created a new image of husband and wife , he compare them with compass . He revolted this against the conventional type of love. Not only he has created a new look in romance but also through new light on this concept. He has shown the height of mysticism. Though mysticism which means that it's a direct institution experience of God through unifying love. After this discussion there is no doubt to say that there are two types of mystical colures. First type of is related to blood and another is based on sexual relationship. Johnson in his 'Lives Of Poets' said about Gray 'Perhaps he was the most learned man in Europe. He was equally acquainted with the elegant and profound parts of science and that not superficially, but thoroughly. He knew every bXanch of History. 'With these lines it has become clear to all about Grays personality. In Gray 'Elegy Written In Country Churchyard' poem such type of relation has shown. When he says

'Their Name, Their Years, Spelt by th 'Unlettered Muse
The Place of fame and elegy supply
And many a holy text around she strews,
That teach the rustic moralist to die. 84

With the help of these lines it has clearly shown that mystical concept related to stream of consciousness. It has a combination of past ,present and future .The stream of consciousness has been defined in various form for example 'H.J.Muller 'the new novel is a withdrawal from external phenomena into the flickering half shades of the authors private world.' According to these lines this concept has totally based on subjective note. Means just as based on inner voice. When somebody miss or remember someone so that will be the height pick of mysticism. When someone will ask and read the unlettered muse, their name, year so the person will once again come in this world and it will be the highest pick of mystical height. Though the man is not in this world even he is present, his presence makes the man to feel that intimacy that he close to that man. It also feel us the importance of absence. If the man is not in this world even then he is always remain present in our memories.

On the other side it can be cleared by Donne's poem 'Presence In Absence. 'It is one of the most celebrated poem of his carrier. In the poem the poet has concentrated on the psychological state of mind .According to the poet mind is the store house of memories. It flesh in our mind and it bring us in the remote incident. Memories are the

blend of past, present and future. With the help of these concept the poet has tried to proved that in the absence of someone, he is present in our memories. Presence In Absence is basically showing the inner voice of the poet when his wife died. He says

of truest mettle

Absence doth join and Time doth settle. '6

With the help of these lines he described the importance of physical absence of his wife has not been able to change their love. Time and Death has no effect on them infect now they can be able to meet at any time. This kind of presence in absence has presented in every type of relations. He ha rejected the power of absence. According to Donne man can die physically but they are with them those who remember them. Such type of thoughts has related to human mind psychologically. Shakespeare well known name in the field of drama which is based on human emotions. His plays are fully colored by human emotions. In Shakespeare's King Lear when Lear asked his three daughters... 'Give me the map there. Know that we have divided In three our kingdom and tis our fast intent. Cordelia.. 'Then poor Cordelia and yet so. Since, I am sure ,my love's More richer then my tongue 'Again she cleared it in this way 'unhappy that I am, I cannot heave My heart into my mouth, I love your majesty, According to my bound ,nor more nor less. '1 Act

With the help of this conversation between father and daughter there also present the concept of presence in absence where daughter has clearly accepted it. After her marriage she will always miss her relation with her father so mystical aspect has not only present in sexual relation but also in other relations too.

After analyzing these facts now in short there is no doubt to say that 'when inner experience in terms of a widely separated from the outer reality then it's a state of mystical approach'. Donne's such types of experience has based on sexuality on the other side in others it has discussed in a different way. For example in Shakespeare's King Lear there is a relationship between father and a daughter extreme height of their emotions. Gray has discussed it in another way where he has shown it with the help of common man. In modern century Eliot a well known 21 century poet has shown this in different way for example he has created a new concept in 'The Love Song OF j. Alfred Prufrock he says

'The Yellow fog rube its back upon the window -panes,

The Yellow Smoke that rubs its muzzle on the window -panes,

Licked its tongue into the corners of the vening'. 16

So in these linesthere has a less logical comparison of the yellow fog and cat. The fog has suffocated Prufrock and cat merged with it to showed desires. In modern world everybody is livening in tension therefore this has shown with the help of this imaginary world. Eliot has refined the earlier theories of the 17th century and created a new concept in the field of mysticism. When the inner experience in terms of a widely separated outer reality then it's a state of mystical attitude. In my opinion after this discussion from Donne to Eliot everybody has tried to proved that this concept has totally based on the height of feelings. So finally before closing the paper through this discussion I am just interested to connect the mystical approach in every relation. After all man has a bundle of feelings, emotions and passions. In the paper I have just tried to connect the topic and through light on these great literary writers. From Donne to Eliot I have shown the different shades and changing status of the mystical relations.

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